

HYBRIDIZED SI-CNF NANOCOMPOSITE AND GRAPHITE AS A HIGH PERFORMANCE ANODE FOR LI-ION BATTERY

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1 General Introduction

Carbonaceous anodic materials have been used for lithium-ion batteries due to their good initial Coulombic efficiency and cycle performance [1-3]. However, much capacity is strongly demanded for applications to the larger energy consuming devices such as electric vehicles. Among many candidate materials, silicon-base materials have attracted huge interest because of the higher capacity (4200 mAh g⁻¹, with the formation of Li₂₂Si₅) than graphite (372 mAh g⁻¹). Nevertheless, silicon anodes suffer from by two major disadvantages: the low electric conductivity and huge volume change during lithium-ion insertion and extraction processes of the lithium-ion battery, leading to pulverizations in the structure. The pulverizations lead to the drastic change of the anode structural morphologies and poor contacts between the Si particles and current collector. Many efforts have been made to overcome these problems by reducing the particle size [4, 5], using silicon-based thin films and nanowires [6, 7], and using composite materials [8-10]. Among them, one of the most promising strategies is to composite nano-sized silicon with a carbon matrix, in which the carbonaceous material acts as both a structural buffer and an electric conductive material. In carbonaceous materials, carbon nanofiber (CNF) was proposed as anode material [11-13]. Compositing Si nanoparticles with CNF is an effective methods to prevent severe pulverization of Si; hindering Si particle aggregation, providing long distance electron conductivity and eliminating the need for conducting additive [14, 15]. However, the discharge capacity of CNF is not so high and the cycling performance is not good because of the high surface area of CNF itself (100~200 m² g⁻¹).

Our research group has proposed a novel solution to moderate volume expansion of anode by growth of CNF on the surface of silicon particles to reduce the

volume expansion by rapping as to provide space among them for absorbing the volume expansion [11]. Jang et al. has demonstrated that the Si-CNF composites showed better performance but still observed capacity decreasing (23%) after 20 cycles because of low electrical contact area between CNFs grown on the surface of Si particles (presumably point contact). In this work, the Si-CNF composites were hybridized with commercial graphite to afford larger contact area between the composites (CNFs on the composites) and graphite (hopefully line contact), for improving of the cycling performance through stable contact characteristic and good electric conductivity of CNF and graphite.

2 Experimental

2.1 Sample Preparation

Nano-sized silicon particles (20 nm and 50 nm, Nanostructured & Amorphous Materials, Inc., USA) were used as starting materials. Helium, methane, carbon monoxide and hydrogen gases were applied for pyrolytic carbon (PyC) coating and CNF growth. PyC coating was carried out in a horizontal furnace using a quartz boat and heated to 900 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ under flowing He gas. When the temperature reached to 900 °C, the gas flow was changed mixed gas of CH₄ and H₂ (4: 1) and maintained for 1 h to coat the PyC on the surface of Si. The reactor was cooled down to room temperature under flowing He gas. The amount of coated PyC was 20.9 wt % for 20 nm Si and 15.6 wt% for 50 nm Si on the weight basis. The obtained PyC-coated Si particles were designated as Si/PyC. Reagent grade iron nitrate enneanhydrate [Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O] (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd, Japan) as the CNF growth catalyst and Si particles were dissolved into ethanol, and then the solution

was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The amount of the catalyst was carefully controlled to support 2 wt % Fe on Si weight basis. After evaporating ethanol at 55 °C, this mixture was dried at 50 °C for 24 h under vacuum. CNFs were synthesized on the Si surface using fixed-bed reactor. The Si/PyC particles with Fe (2 wt %) was placed in the center of horizontal tube furnace and heated to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ under flowing He gas. Then the mixed gases of CO and H₂ were introduced over Si/PyC with Fe catalyst for 30 min. The reactor was cooled down to room temperature in He gas after the CNF growth. The amount of CNF was 71 wt % for 20 nm Si and 47 wt% for 50 nm Si on the weight basis. The obtained composite of Si/PyC with CNF was referred as to Si/PyC/CNF. The addition of composites to MAG (graphite, Hitachi Chemical, Japan) was carried to increase the capacity and improve the cycling performance.

2.2 Analysis and Electrochemical Tests

The surface morphology was observed under transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEM-2100F, JEOL, Japan). Crystallographic properties were measured by X-ray powder diffractometer (CuK α ,Ultima-III, Rigaku, Japan). The galvanostatic charge-discharge was carried out using coin-type cell of CR2032 with two electrodes, where Li metal foil was used as a counter electrode, styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR, trade name BM-400B, ZEON, Japan) which has a high tensile strength, better flexibility and higher thermal stability compared with poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) [16], and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) as a binder system. Coin-type cells were assembled in a free glove using poly-ethylene film (16 μ m thick) as a separator and 1M LiPF₆ in ethylene carbonate (EC)/diethyl carbonate (DEC) (1:1 vol %, Ube Kosan, Japan) as an electrolyte. The electrochemical measurements were performed through charging by constant current-constant voltage (CCCV) and discharging by constant current (CC) with the current density of 30 or 100 mA g⁻¹ in the potential range of 0.003~1.5V versus Li/Li⁺ (Toscat-3100, Toyo-system, Japan) at room temperature.

3 Results and Discussions

XRD profiles of 20 nm Si (20Si), and 50 nm Si (50Si) particles and their derivative composites are shown in Fig. 1. After the pyrolytic carbon coating on Si surface, amorphous carbon peaks were found very weakly, and after the CNF growth on Si/PyC, an intensive peak due to the grown CNF was apparently observed around 26°.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of silicon composites

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs of (a) 20Si/PyC, (b) 20Si/PyC/CNF, (c) 50Si/PyC, and (d) 50Si/PyC/CNF

Figure 2 shows the TEM images of PyC and PyC/CNF composites from the 20 nm Si and 50 nm Si particles. As for the PyC composites, it was found that very thin pyrolytic carbon layer was coated on the surface of the 20 nm and 50 nm silicon particles (Fig. 2 (a) and (c)). Also, CNFs were observed on the surface of the PyC-coated silicon particles (Fig. 2 (b) and (d)).

Fig. 3. 30 cycle performance of (a) 20Si, 20Si/PyC, and 20Si/PyC/CNF and b) 50Si, 50Si/PyC, and 50Si/PyC/CNF (100 mA g^{-1})

Figure 3 shows the 30 cycle performance profiles of the Si/PyC/CNF composites at 100 mA g^{-1} . The 20 nm Si or 50 nm Si particles itself showed inferior capacities and cycle performances. The Si/PyC and Si/PyC/CNF composites also had poor cycle performance because repetitions of swelling and shrinking by insertion and extraction of lithium-ion into the Si composite anode during charging-discharging cycles lead to separation of conductive networks between Si composites.

Figure 4 shows the 30 cycle performance profiles of the mixtures between Si/PyC composites and graphite at 30 mA g^{-1} . As shown in Figure 4a, the 20Si/PyC:MAG=1:9 showed a good cycling stability with a discharge capacity retention of 94.8% after 30 cycles. The 1st cycle Coulombic efficiency was high value of 89.9%. However, 20Si/PyC:MAG=2:8 and

Fig. 4. 30 cycle performance of the mixtures of (a) 20Si/PyC and b) 50Si/PyC composites with MAG at different mixing ratio (30 mA g^{-1})

3:7 samples showed the relatively poor cycling stability which displayed severe decays just after 15 cycles with the discharge capacity retentions of 84.7% and 79.9% after 30 cycles, respectively. Figure 4b shows the cycling performances of the mixtures of 50Si/PyC composite with graphite. Especially 50Si/PyC:MAG=3:7 showed the severe decrease of the cycling performance just after 10 cycles, which was faster than 20Si/PyC/CNF: MAG=3:7, and a discharge capacity retention of 81.8% after 30 cycles. The observed dependence of the cycling performance on the particle size provides direct evidence that larger particles would experience more pulverization and cracking during lithium-ion insertion and extraction processes.

Figure 5 shows the cycling performance profiles of the mixtures of Si/PyC/CNF composites and graphite at 30 mA g^{-1} . In Figure 5a, the 20Si/PyC /-

Fig. 5. 30 cycle performance of the mixtures of a) 20Si/PyC/CNF and b) 50Si/PyC/CNF composites with MAG at different mixing ratio (30 mA g^{-1})

CNF:MAG=1:9 showed a good cycling stability with a discharge capacity retention of 97.7% after 30 cycles. The relatively high 1st cycle Coulombic efficiency of 80.3% was obtained. The retention ratios of 2:8 and 3:7 mixtures were 94.5% and 92.6% after 30 cycles, and the initial Coulombic efficiencies were estimated as 74.2% and 67.5%, respectively. The cycling performances for the mixtures of 50Si/PyC/CNF composite and graphite were similar those for with the mixtures of 20Si/PyC/CNF composite (Fig.5b). The retention ratio of 1:9, 2:8 and 3:7 mixtures are 98.8%, 96.7 % and 95.4%, and the initial Coulombic efficiencies are 77.8 %, 72.1% and 66.9%, respectively. I should be noted that the discharge capacities of all mixture samples were higher than graphite (MAG) itself. Small increase of discharge capacity was observed for MAG after charge-discharge cycling; the SBR-CMC binder might prohibit access of the electrolyte to the surface of graphite at the beginning, and after repeated charge and discharge cycles, well-contact

between the graphite and the electrolyte would be achieved, giving rise to an increase of discharge capacity [17].

Fig. 6. Schematic diagrams of morphological changes of Si/PyC and Si/PyC/CNF composite anodes during lithium-ion charge and discharge cycling

As compared to results in Figure 4 with those in Figure 5, the cycling performance of the mixtures of the Si/PyC/CNF composites with graphite was better than that of the mixtures of Si/PyC. This can be explained that CNFs absorb the volume expansion of silicon particles during lithium-ion insertion, and thus reduce the loss of contact and maintain the electric conductivity between graphite particles and CNFs of Si/PyC/CNF composite as shown in Figure 6. That is, CNFs were considered to shrink during the volume expansion, and to expand to their original status during the volume contraction of the silicon particles. However, the mixtures of Si/PyC with graphite could lose their contact between them because of the gap formation by the volume change of the silicon particles during the charge-discharge cycling. On the other hand, the effect of mixing of the Si/PyC/CNF composites with graphite on the stable cycle performance was considered to be due to firmer contacts between anodic materials for the mixture than Si/PyC/CNF alone. The contact between CNFs and graphite could be in line contacts, although CNFs grown on different silicon particles may contact at a point in the absence of graphite, the point contact would be easily lost by repeated

charge-discharge cycles compared with the line contact, and thus cause inferior cycle performance.

4 Conclusion

In this study, the mixtures of Si/PyC/CNF composites with graphite to improve electrochemical properties were explored. The nano-sized silicon particles were coated with PyC and CNFs were grown on their surface by the chemical vapor deposition. When Si/PyC/CNF composites were hybridized with commercial graphite, the cycling performance of these mixtures was improved due to flexibility and electric conductivity of CNFs. However, the mixtures of Si/PyC composite without CNF were observed fast discharge capacity fading. The good cyclability and high reversible capacity should be resulted from CNFs to compensate the volume expansion of silicon particles and maintain good contact between composites and graphite during lithium insertion and extraction cycles.

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